

THE ROLE OF COLLOQUIAL SPEECH UNITS IN THE POETICS OF A LITERARY WORK (BASED ON THE WORKS OF KHAYRIDDIN SULTON)

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Abstract: This article explores the role of lexical units related to colloquial speech in literary texts and their significance in achieving the author's poetic objectives, illustrated through the works of Khayriddin Sulton.

Keywords: linguopoetic analysis, literary text, colloquial speech, mastery of word usage, expressiveness, imagery, freedom.

It is known that language units differ according to the field of human activity and the nature of speech forms associated with them. During communication in all spheres of daily life, the selection and use of phonetic, lexical-phraseological, and grammatical means in the language differs to some extent. In literary texts, the purposeful selection of language tools leads to the emergence of diverse forms of characters' speech within the text. Naturally, to increase the realism of a literary work, features typical of colloquial speech are also reflected in the speech of the characters. That is, the use of incomplete sentences—mainly in dialogues—mimics, gestures, and the wide use of limited lexical and phraseological units to enhance expressiveness become noticeable. Indeed, in the structure and formation of a text, the author's purpose in constructing the text is of exceptional importance. In the works of Khayriddin Sulton, it is also possible to observe the phonetic, lexical, morphological, and syntactic features of colloquial speech in the language of the characters.

In the following excerpt from a literary text, through the use of a morphological unit, the character's respectful attitude toward interlocutors is evident. This is seen in the habitual use of the suffix “-jon,” which actually expresses affection or endearment. The author uses this morphological form to individualize the character's speech. That is, throughout the work, you will not find a single instance of this character's speech without this suffix. Furthermore, the repeated use of a word with this affix in a vocative function at the end of the text also demonstrates the character's subjective attitude toward the interlocutor. For example:

“Hojijon, please sit on that motorcycle,” he said, pointing to the bearded young man facing his motorcycle, “He will take you in the direction your companions went, you will find them. They haven’t gone far yet, as they just left.” “And if I can’t find them?”

I asked hesitantly. “If you can’t find them, the motorcycle will bring you right back here. I will be waiting here, and if your companions come looking for you, I’ll hold them here too. Oh, hojijon, hojijon-ey!” (“Saodat sohili”)

In the following passage, the colloquial variant of the literary word *kelinoyi* (sister-in-law) as *kennoyi* and the fixed phrase *to‘ng‘izdan to‘q* (“fuller than a pig” – meaning “very insensitive” or “rude”) serve a special expressive function. The word *kennoyi* belongs to colloquial language and points to the naturalness of the character’s speech, while as a restricted lexeme, it also shows the character’s belonging to a specific region. Furthermore, the idiomatic phrases like “*xudo urdi-ketdi*” (God struck and left), “*yetsa – molim, yetmasa – jonim*” (if it’s enough—my wealth, if not—my life), and “*sadqayi ko‘z yosh*” (a sacrifice to your tears) alongside the stable expression *to‘ng‘izdan to‘q*, which carries an insulting meaning, stand out for their uniqueness and catch the reader’s attention for their rarity in the text.

“Let it be even worse! God struck and left, but you are flesh and blood! Never mind, don’t worry, if you don’t have your brother, you have me—your uncle! If it’s enough—my wealth, if not—my life! Oh, don’t cry, *kennoyi*, let your tears be a sacrifice! Even if I’m left without a shroud, the people will find four yards of cloth to bury me. If you die tomorrow, this heartless one wouldn’t even say, ‘Oh, my mother!’ Brother, how much are you short?.. All right, I’ll bring it from home in the morning! Oh, let him end up in the grave instead of being a brother, he’s fuller than a pig!” (“Yo, Jamshid”)

As mentioned above, the freedom in using lexical units characteristic of colloquial speech is the main feature that distinguishes it from other types of speech. In this type of speech, one can see freedom even in the frequent use of restricted lexical units such as curses and insulting words in vocative expressions. In the following, slightly longer, passage, in order to convey the state of the character’s intense anger, the use of restricted units from colloquial speech—namely, dysphemistic expressions—can be observed in the literary text. Especially, the use of vocative expressions carrying an insulting meaning fulfills a highly expressive function in the poetics of the work, clearly expressing strong hatred and playing a distinct stylistic role:

— Speak, you little dog! — he said. His younger brother suddenly raised his head, the lines on his forehead deepened, and he frowned. After a while, as if talking to himself, he said:

— Don't be a disbeliever, your mother is sitting in front of you, be ashamed to face the dog. The old woman turned pale and blushed alternately, her shoulders slumped. Islomboy's jaw trembled: — If I'm not a disbeliever, will I not become even worse, what's it to you, you scoundrel! For your actions, even more than a disbeliever, one would turn into a chulchut!* At his shouting, one of the children lying in the corner woke up with a start, and stared in confusion, rubbing his sleepy eyes. — What is pigskin compared to your shameless face?! In the summer, didn't you swear, "If I ever mention this bastard again, may I die a man," have you forgotten, you oath-breaker! — As Islomboy shouted in burning anger, he felt as if something was being twisted into his temples, and a headache started. — Isn't it better to die swearing than to live this way, you wretch! ("Yo, Jamshid") (Chulchut is a derogatory term, possibly meaning "worse than a disbeliever," conveying deep contempt.)

The passage above also shows that, sometimes, due to the freedom of colloquial speech in a literary text, it becomes impossible to fully express certain lexical units. In such cases, the author uses an ellipsis (three dots) as a punctuation mark to indicate these words.

In the following excerpt from a literary text, the phrase "if you don't die, do a somersault" (o'lmasang, o'mbaloq osh) serves a unique poetic function in the character's speech. It is well known that in everyday life, people often use harsh words expressing the meaning of "may it be even worse for you" to someone who is blamed for bringing trouble upon themselves. However, in this situation, the author uses the phrase "if you don't die, do a somersault" in the character's speech. As is known, in sports, particularly gymnastics, this phrase refers to rolling on the ground in a tucked position using your hands to move your head to the front or back of your body. In daily life, it can also be used to describe a situation where a person, unable to get out of one problem, ends up in an even worse one. Through this restricted unit, the character wants to say to his younger brother that his current situation is even worse than death. This phrase can be seen as an example of the author's individual creative usage: — Oh, what misery! Are you trying to scare me by saying you're going to die? If you don't die, do a somersault! Even if you die, I'll grieve this much, you've really set my heart on fire! ("Yo, Jamshid")

It is known that in spoken language, even onomastic units such as anthroponyms (personal names) are pronounced differently than in written language. In literary texts, in order to ensure the naturalness characteristic of colloquial speech, the author does not overlook this feature. On the contrary, the author makes effective use of this feature in realizing his poetic intention. The writer introduces a young man whose real name is Abduazim but is called “Abdaz” by local residents, incorporating this into the literary text. The author also highlights how his source of daily income is attached to his name as a nickname. This creates a poetic opportunity for the author to introduce the character easily and to make him memorable to the reader:

— I am just an ordinary entrepreneur. I live in Yordonko‘l, and my wife and I cook and sell chicken. We have both fried in butter and grilled options. No complaints about the business; everything is great.

— Excuse me, what is your name and surname?

— Obloqulov Abduazim, but if you say “Abdaz the tobacco seller,” the whole village will know me. (“Ishonch telefoni”)

As seen from the above analysis, the aesthetic function of language has a broader and freer opportunity to be manifested in colloquial speech. In the linguopoetic study of a literary text, analyzing the language units belonging to colloquial speech within the text further demonstrates the writer’s skill and mastery.

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